

15. D. E. CRAGG and J. R. HALL, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1965, **21**, 357.
16. Y. KERMARRIC, *Compt. rend.*, 1964, **258**, 5896.
17. G. BRINK and M. FALK, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1970, **48**, 2090.
18. P. C. RATH and B. K. MOHAPATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 710.
19. P. C. RATH and B. K. MOHAPATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 834.
20. B. SINGH, D. K. SHARMA, U. S. P. SHARMA and B. K. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 764.
21. G. CONTRERAS and R. SCHMIDT, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 1295.
22. M. N. CHAMBERLAIN and J. C. BAILER, Jr., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 6412.
23. P. C. MITCHELL and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 1912.
24. J. LEWIS, R. S. NYHOLM and P. W. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 4590.
25. A. TRRICO and C. PRILE, *Nature*, 1961, **191**, 66.
26. I. BERTINI and A. SARATINI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 1665.
27. C. PRILE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 210.
28. A. SARATINI and I. BERTINI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 359.
29. M. A. BENNETT, R. J. H. CLARK and A. D. J. GOODWIN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 1625.[†]
30. A. TRAMER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1962, **36**, 932.
31. I. BERTINI and A. SARATINI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 1026.
32. M. MERTAN and A. B. P. LEVER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 47.

Determination of Stability Constants of 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphafurazole Complexes with La³⁺, Y³⁺, Pr³⁺, Nd³⁺, Gd³⁺, Dy³⁺

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In the present investigation, potentiometric studies on 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphafurazole and its complexes with some trivalent metal ions have been carried out. The dissociation constants (pK_1 and pK_2) of the reagent and the formation constants ($\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$) of its metal chelates have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bejerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

The titrations were carried out in 75 : 25% (v/v) dioxane-water medium at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and at a constant ionic strength of 0.1 M. Appropriate correction factor for pH meter readings (B values) in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water medium has been applied².

Experimental

The ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphafurazole was prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and the amine in alcohol-DHF mixture for about 2 hr. The crude product was repeatedly crystallised from DMF to get an analytically pure compound with m.p. 220° . The purity of the compound was established by

tlc and elemental analysis. (Found : C, 63.21 ; H, 4.47 ; N, 10.24. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{16}N_2O_4S$; C, 62.71 ; H, 4.51 ; N, 9.98%). The structure of the ligand is,

All the metal perchlorates used were prepared from metal carbonates and perchloric acid of A. R. grade. These were standardised complexometrically by EDTA titrations³.

Other experimental details were the same as in earlier communication⁴.

Results and Discussion

It may be mentioned here that the ligand did not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions described. This was indicated by rapid attainment of equilibrium during the course of titration and by the absence of any significant drift in pH even after 2 hr. This was further confirmed by taking tlc of a sample titration mixture from time to time.

It is the phenolic (OH) group in the ligand which takes part in complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by the metal ion during chelation. As only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated, Y, the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

From the titration curves (Fig. 1), $\bar{n}_d$ values at various B values (pH meter readings) were calculated and the formation curve (B vs $\bar{n}_d$) was plotted. The pK_1 corresponding to phenolic H was obtained by half integral method of $\bar{n}_d = 0.5$. This was further corroborated by plotting the graph of $\log(\bar{n}_d/1 - \bar{n}_d)$ vs B.

From the titration curves (Fig. 1), $\bar{n}$ and pL values for metal-ligand systems were also determined. From the curves $\bar{n}$ vs pL, $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were determined by half integral method. As in the cases of La³⁺, Gd³⁺ and Pr³⁺ complexes, the difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ was found to be less than 1.78 log units. These were computed by least square method and the same are reported in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF
VARIOUS COMPLEXES

Cations	t = 25°		μ = 0.1				
	H ⁺	Gd ³⁺	La ³⁺	Pr ³⁺	Nd ³⁺	Y ³⁺	Dy ³⁺
log K ₁	7.763	8.19	7.90	7.55	5.60	5.90	5.05
log K ₂	—	7.13	7.11	7.30	—	—	—

The order of stability of metal chelates is found to be Gd³⁺ > La³⁺ > Pr³⁺ > Nd³⁺ > Y³⁺ > Dy³⁺.

Fig. 1. Titration curves of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphafurazole.

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References

1. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
2. A. CORSINI and E. J. BILLO, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, 32, 1249.
3. H. A. FLASCHKA, "EDTA Titrations", Pergamon Press, Inc., N.Y., 1959.
4. M. S. MAYADRO and H. S. HUSSAIN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 143.

Conductance of KCl and NaCl in Sucrose + Water, Glucose + Water and Urea + Water Mixtures at Different Temperatures

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STRUCTURAL interactions in ternary system comprising electrolyte-solvent-nonelectrolyte are gaining special attention in recent years. It has been

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observed that nonelectrolyte molecules interact with the ions of the electrolytes in solution¹⁻³. Several polyhydroxy compounds are known to interact with electrolytes in solutions^{1,4}. Definite adducts of many carbohydrates with salts and hydrated oxides of alkali and alkaline earth metals have also been reported^{5,6}. Conductance of electrolyte solutions in the presence of nonelectrolytes have been measured by several workers¹⁻³. The changes in conductance of carbohydrate-electrolyte solutions¹⁰ was attributed to the obstruction of electrical migration of ions by the environmental nonelectrolyte entities^{11,12}.

In the present communication, the ion-solvent interaction of KCl and NaCl have been studied from conductivity data at weight percent of nonelectrolyte (sucrose, glucose) + water (5, 10, 15 and 20) mixtures at 30, 35, 40 and 45° and urea + water at 30 and 35°.

Materials and methods :

The salts used were of E. Merck 'Extra Pure' grade. Sucrose, glucose and urea were of B.D.H. AnalaR grade. The methods for preparation of the solvents and solutions and of measurements were the same as reported earlier¹³. Conductance measurement was of an accuracy of ± 2 in 1000. The concentration range was from 0.01 to 0.001 equiv/lit. Studies above 35° could not be performed in case of urea + water because of hydrolysis.

Results and Discussion

The equivalent conductivity of KCl and NaCl investigated at weight percent of nonelectrolyte (sucrose, glucose and urea) + water mixtures (5, 10, 15 and 20) are found to be linear with $C^{1/2}$ in the concentration range 0.01 to 0.001 mol lit⁻¹. This indicates that the salts are completely ionised. The limiting equivalent conductivity, Λ° , for KCl and NaCl at different compositions and at different temperatures obtained from the usual extrapolation procedure are given in Table 1 along with the values in aqueous solution¹⁴.

From the determined Λ° values, the theoretical slope, S_T , of the plot of Λ vs $C^{1/2}$ at 35° for KCl and NaCl at different solvent compositions has been obtained and compared with the observed slope, S (Table 2). The S value is found to be greater than S_T , which indicates that the observed conductance is less than that of the theoretical value. This difference is of the order : sucrose + water > urea + water > glucose + water, which indicates the structure breaking order also.

The Walden product, $\Lambda^\circ \eta_0$, has been usually employed to study ion-solvent interaction in solution from the conductivity data. $\Lambda^\circ \eta_0$ of both KCl and NaCl at different temperatures and at different solvent compositions are given in Table 3. The results show that it is maximum in case of glucose +